

ABRASIVE WATERJET MACHING SMALL FEATURES IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

For most composite materials, their non-homogenous structures provoke complications during many machining operations. The majority of composite materials use hard and brittle fibers such as carbon, graphite and glass which can result in excessive wear on tools during traditional mechanical machining [1] and large heat affected zones (HAZ) when laser beam [2] or electric discharge machining [3]. The defects produced from these processes result in undesirable surface finishes, strength degradation, delamination, dimensional errors, and changes in the substrates micro-structure. Abrasive waterjet machining (AWJM) of composite materials is an attractive alternative method due to its many advantages over mainstream machining such as no HAZ, no tooling wear, rapid etch rates and its ability to cut virtually any composite material. The current research examined the cut surface morphology of three composite materials: i) a carbon fiber epoxy, 60% fiber by weight, ii) a polypropylene long-glass fiber, 30% fiber by weight, and iii) a carbon fiber vinyl ester, 50% fiber by weight. A novel aspect of the study was the use of a prototype 254 μm micro-abrasive waterjet machining (μAWJM) nozzle. The objective was to analyze the feature resolution and cut surface morphology at varying feature sizes and traverse speeds. The morphological differences between high and low traverse speeds are discussed with respect to composite material properties, and an optimal machining configuration for small features is proposed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Abrasive waterjet machining (AWJM) is a non-traditional machining technology that was first proposed by Smith [4], and then later refined by Tirrell in the 1940's [5]. However, due to technological limitations of the time, the waterjet was limited to surface finishing and rough cutting operations. Not until the 1980's did abrasive waterjet (AWJ) systems become more commercialized due to the addition of abrasives which drastically increased the material removal rate [6]. The advantages of AWJM are no heat affected zones (HAZ), negligible reaction forces when cutting, environmentally benign, relatively large cutting depths and etch rates, capable of cutting virtually any material, and typically does not require secondary or finishing machining operations. The next advancement in AWJM is miniaturization of the AWJ and the development of micro-abrasive-waterjet (μAWJ) machining. Many AWJ manufactures have developed this technology, but are mostly in the prototyping/early development phases due to complications associated with reducing the orifice and nozzle sizes.

Many studies have looked at machining composite materials using AWJs. A majority of the AWJM/composite studies have focused on AWJM epoxy carbon fiber/graphite fiber unidirectional laminates, with an emphasis on quantifying the relationship between AWJM operating parameters and surface characteristics [7] [8-14]. Other unidirectional thermoplastic and thermoset composite materials that have been analyzed during AWJ cutting operations are: Kevlar/epoxy [15], Kevlar/phenolic [16], cotton/phenolic [17], and glass/thermoset resin WM-125 TA [18, 19]. The bulk of the research on AWJM polymer matrix composites has been on unidirectional fibers, with relatively little work reported on randomly-oriented fiber composites.

All previous studies on AWJ cutting of composite material have used nozzles larger than 760 μm . These larger nozzles generate features that are larger than those typical of micro-abrasive-waterjet machining (μAWJM). Miller performed a study investigating μAWJM of composite materials, however his analysis was purely proof of concept, and did not analyze the morphological characteristics of the cutting surfaces [20]. In addition, Miller used a suspension jet abrasive system, which is rarely used in manufacturing due to its lower erosion rate when compared to injection systems.

The current study analyzed the morphological characteristics of small features cut using a prototype μAWJ nozzle over a range of composite substrates.

2 METHODOLOGY

The experiments examined the AWJ cutting performance of three composite materials: i) 1.2 mm CF/epoxy laminate (CFRP epoxy), ii) chopped glass fiber/polypropylene thermoplastic composite (PPLGF30), and iii) a 50% by fiber by weight CF/vinyl composite (CF SMC). Their properties are presented in Table 1.

	Fiber Volume Percentage by Weight (V_f)	Fiber Orientation	Manufacturing Technique	Thickness
Carbon fiber/epoxy (CFRP epoxy)	60%	Uni-directional laminate ([0/90/0] _s), continuous fiber	Compression molded	1.2 mm \pm 0.02 mm
Long-glass fiber/polypropylene (PPLGF30)	30%	Random oriented discontinuous fibers	Compression molded	3.75 mm \pm 0.02 mm
Carbon fiber/vinyl sheet molding compound (CF SMC)	50%	Random oriented discontinuous fibers	Compression molded	6mm \pm 0.02 mm

Table 1: Composite materials.

Based on the literature, it was determined that optimal cutting performance could be achieved by using a small nozzle and abrasive size [21], slow traverse speed [17], small stand-off distance (SOD) [22], and high pressures [8]. The nozzle used in the experiments was a prototype micro-nozzle from OMAX Corp. (Seattle, WA, USA) with an inside nozzle diameter $d_n = 254 \mu\text{m}$. The abrasive used was Barton hard rock garnet with a nominal size of 75 μm . This garnet was used because it exhibited high repeatability between samples in preliminary tests. The highest pressure of the AWJ apparatus (OMAX 2626 Jet Machining Center) with the attached nozzle was 225 MPa. The modifying factor used in the

experiments was traverse speed. The experimental conditions are summarized in Table 2. The maximum traverse speed of the AWJ apparatus was 4000 mm/min.

Parameter	Value
Nozzle Size	254 micron
Abrasive	75 micron Barton hard rock garnet
Abrasive flow rate (AFR)	0.054 kg/min
Pressure	225 MPa
Traverse Speed	Variable
Stand-off Distance (SOD)	1 mm
Submerged Machining	No

Table 2: Experimental Parameters and Conditions.

2.1 Traverse Speed Calibration and Testing

Since various composite materials were used in the experiments, preliminary experiments were necessary to determine the maximum speed to achieve through-cuts for each material. The traverse speeds tested were 200, 400, 800, 1000, 1500, 2000, 2500, 3000, 3500 and 4000 mm/min.

Material	Maximum Traverse Speed [mm/min]
CFRP epoxy	4000
PPLGF30	3000
CF SMC	1000

Table 3: Maximum material traverse speeds for through-cuts.

2.2 Assessment of Cut Resolution and Quality of Machined Features

The purpose of these experiments was to assess the effects of varying traverse speed when machining small features. The geometry of the machined features were squares of various sizes - 10, 8, 4, 2, and 1 mm side lengths. The fastest traverse speeds were based on the maximums shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** The slowest traverse speeds (Table 5) were chosen based on previous trials.

Material	Maximum Traverse Speed [mm/min]
CFRP epoxy	4000
PPLGF30	3000
CF SMC	1000

Table 4: Maximum traverse speed used in the machining of square features.

Nominal Square Feature Size (mm)	Minimum Traverse Speed [mm/min]
10	24
8	24
4	12
2	6
1	3

Table 5: Minimum traverse speed used in the machining of square features.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Traverse Speed Calibration and Testing

3.1.1 1.2 mm, 6 Ply CF/Epoxy Composite – CFRP Epoxy

A qualitative assessment of the cut quality on the CFRP epoxy laminate showed acceptable results up to traverse speeds of 4000 mm/min when machining straight cuts. Slight striations appeared on the cut surfaces for traverse speeds of 2,500 mm/min and above, but disappeared at 2,000 mm/min under the machining conditions in Table 2. This composite was by far the easiest and fastest to cut, but had delamination problems during the piercing process as discussed below.

3.1.2 Chopped Random Fiber/Polypropylene Composite – PPLGF30

The high ductility of the chopped fiber composite resisted erosion more than the CFRP epoxy laminate, and had a maximum traverse speed of around 3000 mm/min. Burr formation on the exit of the cut was present at all traverse rates.

3.1.3 50% Fiber by Weight/Vinyl Composite – CF SMC

The thickest material examined was the CF SMC composite, having a thickness of 6 mm. Under the prescribed machining conditions shown in Table 2, the maximum through pierce traverse speed was 1000 mm/min along a straight line profile. Kerf striations were apparent at the 1000 mm/min traverse speed resulting in a very rough surface finish. Although the striations never fully disappeared, even at traverse speeds as low as 400 mm/min, they were greatly reduced.

3.2 Maximum Resolution and Cut Quality of Machined Features

This section compares identical features under identical machining conditions with the exception of traverse speed. The machining conditions can be found in Table 2, Table 4 and Table 5. The higher quality finishes and feature definitions were due to lower traverse speeds in all of the tests.

3.2.1 1.2 mm, 6 Ply CF/Epoxy Composite – CFRP Epoxy

Figure 1 compares 2 mm square features machined at two extreme traverse speeds. The greater resolution at the slower traverse speed can be attributed to allowing sufficient time for the motor controllers and CNC servo motors time to stabilize after changing direction (i.e. vibrational effects).

Figure 1: Nominal 2 mm machined feature in 1.2 mm thick CFRP epoxy laminate: a. high traverse speed (4000 mm/min) b. low traverse speed (6 mm/min).

The square holes were programmed to have a width of 2 mm, but due to jet dispersion and the absence of tooling offset compensation, the square dimensions were greater than 2 mm. Additionally, the corners of the squares are not sharp due to the radius of the jet. These two characteristics: i) increased feature width, and ii) rounded corners, are common among all the materials and features.

Figure 2 shows that delamination occurred at both high and low traverse speeds, propagating from both the entrance and exit pierces. It was also observed that the delamination was adversely affected by the proximity of subsequent nearby pierces.

Figure 2: Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) of cut surface for the nominal 2 mm size feature: a. traverse speed (4000 mm/min) b. Traverse Speed 6 mm/min

Figure 3 shows garnet particles trapped in a crack caused by inter-ply delamination between a 0° and 90 degree oriented fibers. A composition analysis (EDX) was completed on the particulates, and revealed that they are composed of iron, silicon, calcium and oxygen. The silicon and oxygen atoms correlates to abrasive garnet used, while the iron and calcium can be attributed to minerals within the water. This phenomena was also be observed by Shanmugam et al. [13]. The use of smaller abrasives that accompany the use of smaller waterjet nozzles suggests that this particle trapping may increase with decreasing abrasive particle size.

Figure 3: Particles caught in cracks of the CFRP epoxy laminate.

One method to reduce entrance piercing delamination is to clamp a sacrificial layer to the top of the substrate, such as 1 mm steel sheet. This has been shown to work when cutting composite materials [23] and piercing brittle materials such as glass with an abrasive waterjet [24].

3.2.2 Chopped Random Fiber Composite – PPLGF30

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show that entrance and exit shapes of the nominal 1 mm features in the PPLGF30 composite were less well defined than those in the carbon fiber laminate (Fig. 1). Another notable feature of the chopped fiber composite was the amount of burr formation at the exit side of the feature (Fig. 6).

Figure 4: Nominal 1 mm square feature profiles in PPLGF30 composite, traverse speed 3000 mm/min: a. top surface b. bottom surface.

Figure 5: 1mm Square feature profiles in PPLGF30 composite, traverse speed: 3 mm/min. a. top surface b. bottom surface.

Figure 6 compares the surface finishes and kerf profiles of a 1mm machined feature in the PPLGF30 composite. It is apparent that the geometry resolution and surface finish is much higher with the slow traverse rate. The SEM micrographs clearly define the fibrous nature of the material and burr formation at the exit jet.

Figure 6: SEM of cut surface for PPLGF30 composite, nominal 1 mm feature: a. traverse speed 3000 mm/min, b. traverse speed 3 mm/min

3.2.3 50% Fiber by Weight Vinyl Composite

Figure 7 and Figure 8 illustrate the improved feature profiles when machining the relatively thick (6 mm) CF SMC composite at slow traverse speed.

Figure 7: CF SMC composite, traverse speed 1000 mm/min: a. top surface, b. bottom surface.

Figure 8: CF SMC composite, traverse speed 3 mm/min: a. top surface, b. bottom surface.

Figure 9 shows that the slow traverse speed produced a much better surface finish, kerf taper, and geometry resolution.

Figure 9: Comparison between two cut edge surfaces at different traverse speeds: a. slow traverse speed (12 mm/min), b. fast traverse speed (1000 mm/min).

The CF SMC composite shared common features with both the CFRP epoxy laminate and the PPLGF30; i.e. harder fibers, as with the carbon fiber/epoxy, and the random fiber orientation of the glass fiber/polypropylene. Figure 9 shows that delamination damage occurred near the surface of the CF SMC composite, suggesting that brittle composites are more sensitive to delamination damage when abrasive waterjet machining regardless of fiber orientation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

AWJ machining of composite materials is a viable approach for the machining of intermediate-sized features in composite materials. Calibration must be made of various machining parameters to optimize surface finish, reduce delamination and increase productivity. This paper assessed the cut quality at the two ends of the machining spectrum, associated with low and high traverse speeds. It was concluded that:

- Delamination of laminate composites is more likely at higher traverse speeds.
- Delamination is more likely in relatively brittle materials.
- Small abrasive particles are susceptible to becoming trapped in interlaminar cracks.
- Burrs form when small features are machined in ductile composites
- Feature resolution decreases when machining ductile composites in comparison to brittle composites under the same machining conditions.
- Control of machining stage vibration/resolution has significant impact on feature resolution.

It should be noted that the relatively low through cut speeds are only applicable to μ AWJM, due to the relatively lower jet energy resulting from the small jet size – larger nozzles are capable of very high traverse speeds when machining composite materials. These experiments form the basis for future research on developing analytical models to predict delamination, surface roughness and burr formation.

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REFERENCES

- [1] R. Teti, "Machining of Composite Materials," *CIRP Annals - Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 51, pp. 611-634, 2002.
- [2] J. Mathew, G. L. Goswami, N. Ramakrishnan, and N. K. Naik, "Parametric studies on pulsed Nd:YAG laser cutting of carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites," *Journal of Materials Processing Tech*, vol. 89, pp. 198-203, 1999.
- [3] Y. H. Guu, H. Hocheng, N. H. Tai, and S. Y. Liu, "Effect of electrical discharge machining on the characteristics of carbon fiber reinforced carbon composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 36, pp. 2037-2043, 2001.
- [4] E. V. Smith, "Liquid blasting," ed: Google Patents, 1936.
- [5] L. L. Tirrell, "Method and apparatus for sand blasting," ed: Google Patents, 1940.
- [6] M. A. Hashish, M. J. Kirby, and Y. H. Pao, "Method and apparatus for forming a high velocity liquid abrasive jet," ed: Google Patents, 1987.
- [7] M. Ramulu and D. Arola, "Water jet and abrasive water jet cutting of unidirectional graphite/epoxy composite," *Composites*, vol. 24, pp. 299-308, 1993.
- [8] M. Ramulu and D. Arola, "The influence of abrasive waterjet cutting conditions on the surface quality of graphite/epoxy laminates," *International Journal of Machine Tools and Manufacture*, vol. 34, pp. 295-313, 1994.
- [9] D. Arola and M. Ramula, "Machining-induced surface texture effects on the flexural properties of a graphite/epoxy laminate," *Composites*, vol. 25, pp. 822-834, 1994.
- [10] I. Conner, M. Hashish, and M. Ramula, "Abrasive Waterjet Machining of Aerospace Structural Sheet and Thin Plate Materials," in *2003 WJTA American Waterjet Conference*, Houston, Texas, 2003, pp. 470-479.
- [11] E. Lemma, L. Chen, E. Siores, and J. Wang, "Study of cutting fiber-reinforced composites by using abrasive water-jet with cutting head oscillation," *Composite Structures*, vol. 57, pp. 297-303, 2002.
- [12] D. K. Shanmugam and S. H. Masood, "An investigation on kerf characteristics in abrasive waterjet cutting of layered composites," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 209, pp. 3887-3893, 2009.
- [13] D. K. Shanmugam, T. Nguyen, and J. Wang, "A study of delamination on graphite/epoxy composites in abrasive waterjet machining," *Composites Part A*, vol. 39, pp. 923-929, 2008.
- [14] M. Saleem, H. Bougherara, L. Toubal, F. Cénac, and R. Zitoun, "Analysis of Stresses in CFRP Composite Plates Drilled with Conventional and Abrasive Water Jet Machining," *Materials Science Forum*, vol. 763, pp. 127-143, 2013.
- [15] M. Shukla and P. B. Tambe, "Predictive modelling of surface roughness and kerf widths in abrasive water jet cutting of Kevlar composites using neural network," *International Journal of Machining and Machinability of Materials*, vol. 8, pp. 226-246, 01/01/ 2010.
- [16] M. A. Azmir, A. K. Ahsan, and A. Rahmah, "Effect of abrasive water jet machining parameters on aramid fibre reinforced plastics composite," *International Journal of Material Forming*, vol. 2, pp. 37-44, 2008.
- [17] J. Wang, "Abrasive Waterjet Machining of Polymer Matrix Composites – Cutting Performance, Erosive Process and Predictive Models," *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, vol. 15, pp. 757-768, 1999.
- [18] M. A. Azmir and A. K. Ahsan, "Investigation on glass/epoxy composite surfaces machined by abrasive water jet machining," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 198, pp. 122-128, 2008.
- [19] M. A. Azmir and A. K. Ahsan, "A study of abrasive water jet machining process on glass/epoxy composite laminate," *Journal of Materials Processing Tech*, vol. 209, pp. 6168-6173, 2009.
- [20] D. S. Miller, "Micromachining with abrasive waterjets," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 149, pp. 37-42, 2004.

- [21] R. Kovacevic, R. Mohan, and Y. M. Zhang, "Cutting Force Dynamics as a Tool for Surface Profile Monitoring in AWJ," *Journal of Engineering for Industry*, vol. 117, p. 340, 1995.
- [22] N. S. Guo, H. Louis, and G. Meier, "Abrasive water jet cutting — methods to calculate cutting performance and cutting efficiency," *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences and Geomechanics Abstracts*, vol. 32, pp. A85-A85, 1995.
- [23] M. Hashish, "Machining of advanced composites with abrasive waterjets," *Manufacturing review*, vol. 2, pp. 142-150, 1989.
- [24] J. Schwartzenruber and M. Papini, "Abrasive waterjet micro-piercing of borosilicate glass," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, vol. 219, pp. 143-154, 2015.